

IBPG - Darwin

The Institute of Biopaleogeography
named under Charles R. Darwin

IBPG 22 (2024) 1-86

E-ISSN 2956-4573

Tourism as an instrument for valuing, and disseminating natural, and cultural heritage

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Publisher's Address:

Scientific Publishing House DARWIN at The Institute
22, Adama Mickiewicza Street, 78-520 Złocieniec,
District Drawski, West Pomerania, Poland

Cite of this article:

Fabio Rossano Dario, Maria Cristina Veiga De Vincenzo. Tourism as an instrument for valuing, and disseminating natural, and cultural heritage. *The Institute of Biopaleogeography named under Charles R. Darwin 22 (2024) 1-86*

ABSTRACT

Why is it important to know the geomorphodiversity, the geodiversity, the hydrological, and the biological diversity of the region we visit? This paper is a photographic summary of several scientific, and touristic expeditions carried out in recent years in different ecosystems in America, Europe, Asia, and Africa. The main objective is to show the importance of the relationship between knowledge about the environment, and its resources, with the scenic beauty of the landscape of natural environments, translated into a huge number of rivers, streams, and crystalline lakes connected by a series of cascades, and waterfalls, embedded in a network of mountains of exuberant geological formation, deserts, and forests rich in plant, and animal species.

Keywords: Tourism, environment, ecology, natural resources, geology

INTRODUCTION

For economist Jost Krippendorf (1938-2003), creator of the concept of sustainable tourism, the tourist is an occasional traveler whose destination is the place, and local culture. Krippendorf advocated responsible, and conscious tourism, for the benefit, and good coexistence between visitors, and those visited, with appreciation, and deep respect for differences. In his book “Sociology of Tourism” [1], Krippendorf presents a proposal for the humanization of tourism, where there are new possibilities for leisure and tourist travel. However, for the author, the logic of the tourism industry imposes the culture of the traveler and reproduces in leisure the same commercial relations that are characteristic, and every day of industrial society. The meeting of cultures, the traveler, and the visited, promoted by tourism, would find the place of experience of otherness, tolerance, and peace.

Krippendorf devoted his life to understanding the social nature of tourism and travel. Aside from the economic interests of this industry, he acknowledges that one of the social roots of tourism depends on its logic of recreation. Tourists need to escape from the humdrum routine of daily life, not only to rest but also to validate the rules of their society. Krippendorf argues convincingly that any travel initiates with a previous infrastructure which not only facilitates the displacement but encourages new forms of relationships.

The influences of Sigmund Freud (1856-1939), and the principle of homeostasis [2] were of paramount importance at the time of drawing the studies of Krippendorf. Similarly, to this, the possibility of traveling elsewhere, outside the home, represents a basic need of ego. In so doing, the world not only is appreciated in another way, but some creative forces pave the way for the mind not to collapse. The second point in importance seems to be the encounter between hosts, and guests, although the author does not use these terms. Krippendorf recognizes that holidays, as social construes, exert considerable influence at the time of shaping the tourist consciousness. If travelers rest beyond the boundaries of their homes, this represents a tri-partite fragmentation among the following three axioms: working there, dwelling here, and resting in another place. The act of traveling emulates the psychological need of extolling the responsibility toward the boundaries of self. In third place, the possibility of traveling opens the doors to social recognition and a higher status. Those people, whatever the case may be, who

are restricted from taking holidays or traveling abroad are less important for cultural values than mobile subjects. The social forces not only reify but frame the psychological drives to be systematically fulfilled [3].

Over centuries, intellectuals rested their reflections on the testimonies of travels as other travelers have formulated them. Whether medieval or pre-industrial travel experiences were used to delineate the epistemology of the whole social sciences in Europe, the viewpoint of tourists is neglected as naïve or subject to the lack of objectivity. Why are travels now not taken into consideration by epistemologists? Are modern tourists more naïve or enrooted in a wide variety of prejudices? [4].

The travels enable our curiosity to discover new cultures, and landscapes, as well as the stories this displacement generates [5]. Ewa Mazierska [6] explores the epistemology of past travels to exert criticism on the current social fabric. Mazierska reviews the existent specialized literature that points out tourism as a hedonistic industry, and she alerts, that there are many ways of exploring the visited spaces. The role of travelers and their way of proximity to each other are important in analyzing the effects of tourism on society. The discussion is given by the extent curiosity triggers the process of discovery [4].

Tourism was born from the human need for leisure, and breaking routines. However, capitalism appropriated this need, creating the tourism production chain. Travel agencies, hotel chains, airlines, and a myriad of actors in the lucrative marketing, and sales of conventional tourism create and recreate profitable anti-daily hubs, generally quite different from the true appearance, and culture of the travelers [4]. The market has monopolized the lives of laypeople. Commoditized to be offered as a product, the social bond has been undermined. Now, most of the subjects are not traveling to discover new landscapes, but by fagocitating their own ethnocentrism [7], and in many situations, they have placed the environment, its natural resources, and the traditional populations of the places visited at serious risk.

According to Janusz Zdebski, Rector of The Academy of Physical Education in Kraków, Poland [8], tourism manifests man's aspirations to experience something unusual, something extraordinary; to have rich experiences, and impressions, or simply to feel deep emotions. This uniqueness is depicted in the Himalayan landscapes, the charms of a tropical beach, experiencing emotions while visiting an art gallery, or by witnessing the individuality of the people encountered along the tourist path. Tourist activity can have various effects. These change people, but also, they change other people encountered along the way. Tourism represents a goal, but it can also serve as an instrument of educational activity. Tourism changes the landscape. For the purpose of tourist movement special infrastructures are prepared; people build tourist housing developments and develop mountain slopes, and water routes so they are accessible to tourists. Heavy tourist traffic leads to the devastation of the natural environment, but ironically it can also protect both the natural environment and the cultural environment.

Krippendorf analyzes tourism based on the following subsystems: sociocultural, ecological, economic, and political. These subsystems can be reorganized with a view to more responsible, integrated tourism capable of providing unique experiences to the people of both sending and receiving regions [4]. Following the perspective of sustainable tourism, we have distinct types of activities, such as ecotourism, contemplative tourism, cultural tourism, and scientific tourism.

Sustainable tourism aims to observe the natural resources of the environment in question, without causing risks or damage to natural resources, and the traditional populations that live there. Prior research can be added to this practice to acquire knowledge of the natural resources,

and culture of the indigenous people. The main objective is to increase knowledge and explore historical, natural, and urban landscapes, which will serve as an instrument for valuing and disseminating the natural, and cultural heritage of the areas visited.

Previous research for tourism in natural environments can be grouped into different topics, which in this paper we summarize as geodiversity, hydrodiversity, and biodiversity. In general, these topics are related to the activities of investigating geoparks, relief, and rock formations, bird watching, identifying wild animal tracks, observing water resources, and vegetation, exploring caves, observing cave paintings, of historical sites, and the interaction of surrounding human communities. The research must be started before the trip, for better use in the encounter of objects, and in the search for new knowledge, and discoveries. The level of specificity is relative to the area, and the degree of interest. This practice, where the traveler visits natural environments in search of relaxation, and well-being, adding knowledge about natural resources, and biodiversity, contributing to greater awareness of nature conservation, and the importance of harmonious relationships between fauna, and flora, and present traditional communities, can be a great incentive for contemplative, cultural, and scientific tourism.

Geodiversity

Why is it important to know the geomorphodiversity, and geodiversity of the region we visit? Geomorphodiversity refers to the variety of landforms, and morphological processes characterizing the landscape. Geodiversity is recognized as an important aspect of nature conservation and is a material consideration in planning decisions in developed countries. In recent decades, many researchers have turned their attention to the definition of geodiversity, and its relationship to biodiversity, natural environment protection, ecosystem services, and geotourism. In the emerging science of geodiversity, geomorphodiversity evaluates the shape of the surface features of a place or region. Different geomorphological landforms may occur in a geographical environment that creates a variety of landforms called geomorphodiversity. Therefore, geodiversity is the natural range of geomorphological, geological, hydrological, and soil features [9-15].

Some studies aim to quantify geodiversity on a continental scale and identify regions with a diverse set of abiotic resources, that is, high geodiversity. Similar to biodiversity hotspots, such areas are termed geodiversity hotspots when they undergo significant anthropogenic pressure [16]. The identification of such areas is important for future conservation efforts [17] and for tourist development. The diversity of landforms is included in the widely used definition of geodiversity. In some studies, the geomorphological component of environmental diversity is termed geomorphological diversity or geomorphodiversity [18].

Geotourism is a tourist segment that has the geological heritage as its main attraction and aims at its protection through the conservation of its resources, and tourist awareness. Tourism in geoparks is one of the most widespread scientific tourism practices in the world. These geoparks have landscapes of international geological importance. However, when visiting a geopark or simply a park with geological features that arouse curiosity, the focus should not be on geology alone. The purpose of scientific tourism in an area of geological richness is to explore, develop, and celebrate the relationships between the geological heritage, and all other natural, cultural, and intangible heritage aspects of the area.

The Grand Canyon is not just an spectacular erosion carved primarily by the Colorado River and is not limited to the incredible scenic beauty. The Grand Canyon is one of the greatest examples of geoparks. The History of the Grand Canyon begins about 2 billion years ago when igneous, and metamorphic rocks were formed. Then, layer upon layer of sedimentary rocks were laid on top of these basement rocks. Nearby rock outcrops suggest 1,219 to 2,438 m of sedimentary layers from the “Age of Dinosaurs” once covered the Grand Canyon area. Cenozoic Era (the “Age of Mammals”) layers are limited to the western Grand Canyon, and terraces near the river itself. Regarding the formation of the Grand Canyon, research using apatite fission-track dating [19] revealed that two of the three middle segments, the Hurricane segment, and the Eastern Grand Canyon, formed between 70, and 50 million years ago, and between 25, and 15 million years ago, respectively. Grand Canyon is considered one of the finest examples of arid-land erosion in the world. Incised by the Colorado River, the canyon is immense, averaging 1,200 m deep for its entire 450 km. However, the significance of the Grand Canyon is not limited to its geology [20, 21] (**Photos 1-6**).

Sedona is a beautiful city located in Arizona, United States, and that lies within the Coconino National Forest. It is best known for its surreal landscape, with amazing mountains that are large clusters of red sandstone. Before the red rock was turned into rock, it was all soft mud and sand. Over a 320-million-year period changes in nature helped transform the sand, and mud into something incredibly beautiful. Sea levels rose and fell during this time, and with each rise, and fall mud was added. During the sea level rise, the mud would be washed in, and then when it receded the wind brought in layers of sand. After years of this happening over, and over again, the sediment was transformed into hard rock. The red rocks of Sedona are formed by a unique layer of rock known as the Schnebly Hill Formation. This geological formation is a dark red sandstone, 240 to 300 m thick, that is the major component of the "Red Rocks" of Sedona [22, 23] (**Photos 7-10**).

Triglav National Park is one of the oldest, and largest national parks in Europe [24], and is located in the northwestern part of Slovenia, respectively the southeastern part of the Alpine massif. Mount Triglav, the highest peak of the Julian Alps, stands almost in the middle of the park [25-32]. The Triglav National Park is an area of varied relief that is manifested in a wealth of natural forms: crystal clear water remains of virgin forests, high-altitude ridges, and summits, glacier-carved valleys, mountain lakes, raised bogs, etc. The forest covers two-thirds of the Park's territory, overgrowing valley floors, steep slopes, and high-altitude plateaus [33] (**Photos 11-14**).

In the mountains of Zion National Park, located in the state of Utah, United States, the tourist can contemplate massive sandstone cliffs of cream, pink, and red that soar into a brilliant blue sky (**Photos 15-18**). Zabriskie Point is a part of the Amargosa Range located east of Death Valley in Death Valley National Park in California, United States, noted for its erosional landscape. It is composed of sediments from Furnace Creek Lake, which dried up 5 million years ago, long before Death Valley came into existence (**Photos 19-20**). Regional mountain building to the west influenced the climate to become more, and more arid, causing the lake to dry up, and creating a dry lake. Subsequent widening, and sinking of Death Valley, and the additional uplift of today's Black Mountains tilted the area. This provided the necessary relief to accomplish the erosion that produced the badlands we see today.

Death Valley is a desert valley in Eastern California, in the northern Mojave Desert, bordering the Great Basin Desert. It is thought to be the hottest place on Earth during summer [34]. Death Valley is home to the Timbisha tribe of Native Americans, formerly known as the

Panamint Shoshone, who have inhabited the valley for at least the past millennium. Death Valley is a down-dropped block of land between two mountain ranges. It lies at the southern end of a geological trough, Walker Lane, which runs north to Oregon. The valley is bisected by a right-lateral strike-slip fault system, comprising the Death Valley Fault, and the Furnace Creek Fault. The eastern end of the left lateral Garlock Fault intersects the Death Valley Fault. Furnace Creek and the Amargosa River flow through part of the valley and eventually disappear into the sands of the valley floor (**Photos 21-24**).

Yosemite National Park is an icon of America's majestic natural beauty. The park, located in California, welcomes millions of visitors each year, drawn to its dramatic waterfalls, giant sequoias, abundant wildlife, and awe-inspiring cliffs, like Half Dome, and El Capitan. The landscape of Yosemite National Park is a product of its unique geology, resulting from glacial erosion of the underlying granite. Iconic landforms such as Yosemite Valley, Yosemite Falls, Bridalveil Fall, El Capitan, Half Dome, and Cathedral Peak are known throughout the world. Besides their natural beauty, these icons are also important sites for studying and understanding the geological history of the Sierra Nevada mountain range. Yosemite preserves a fascinating geologic story hundreds of millions of years in the making. Many forces, including water, ice, and even daily temperature changes, have worked to sculpt- sometimes gradually, sometimes catastrophically granite bedrock of Yosemite to form the stunning features that we see today (**Photos 25-28**).

Yosemite National Park is located within the heart of the Sierra Nevada, the largest fault-block mountain range in the United States. Trending northwest-southeast for about 500 km, the Sierra Nevada traverses half the length of California, with the Central Valley to the west, and the Basin, and Range Province to the east. It is an asymmetric mountain range with a long, gentle western slope, and a short, steep eastern escarpment. It is 80 to 130 km wide and extends in elevation from near sea level along its western edge about 4,000 m along the crest in the Yosemite area, and more than 4,000 m along the crest in Sequoia, and Kings Canyon National Parks. The highest peak in the Sierra Nevada, and the continental United States, is 4,421 m tall Mount Whitney in Sequoia National Park. Mount Lyell, the highest peak in Yosemite National Park, rises about 4,000 m above sea level. Geologically, the Sierra Nevada is a huge block of the Earth's crust that is bounded on its east side by a fault system, along which the Sierra has been uplifted, and tilted westward. This combination of uplift, and tilt, which is the underlying geologic process that created the present range, is still occurring today (**Photos 29-30**).

Steamboat Rock State Park is a park located in Washington State, United States. The park takes its name from the landscape's dominating feature, Steamboat Rock, a basalt butte that rises 240 m above the lake that nearly surrounds it. During the last ice age, the monolith stood as an island in the new bed of the Columbia River where it had been diverted by ice dams. Once the dams burst creating massive floods, and the Scablands, the Columbia returned to its original course, leaving Steamboat Rock as a prominent feature of the dry Grand Coulee (**Photos 31, 32**).

High mountains, deep rainforests, alpine lakes, and lush waterfalls are the hallmarks of the evergreen Washington State. Yet travel to the dry scablands of the state's east side, trace your way up a mysterious gorge, and you'll come to one of the nation's most spectacular geologic sites: Dry Falls, the skeleton of the world's largest waterfall: five km of cliffs that once roared with more water than all the rivers of the world combined. During the Ice Age, glaciers to the north blocked the Columbia River, forcing it to find a new route. The river, swollen from melting glacial ice, began to carve a new channel. Melting glaciers formed a huge lake (Lake

Missoula). Eventually, the ice dam broke, unleashing floods up to 10 times the combined flow of all the rivers of the world into eastern Washington, and Oregon. It was like a firehose that carved through the new channel opened by the Columbia. The turbulent water enlarged the channel and created huge waterfalls. When the last flood subsided, large areas of eastern Washington were left scarred with dry channels, called coulees: the Grand Coulee is the largest. Cutting across the coulee is Dry Falls. This 5.5 km wide, and over 120 m tall group of cliffs was at one time the largest waterfall in the world (**Photos 33, 34**).

The Serra da Capivara National Park, located in the State of Piauí, Brazil, is one of the main geoparks in Latin America. The region borders two major geological formations: the Maranhão-Piauí sediment basin, and the peripheral depression of the São Francisco River, and is endowed with a diversity of relief vegetation, and landscapes of breathtaking beauty, and dotted with exceptional views of the surrounding valleys, mountains, and plains. Many of the numerous rock shelters in the Serra da Capivara National Park are decorated with cave paintings, some more than 25,000 years old. They are an outstanding testimony to one of the oldest human communities of South America [35-39] (**Photos 35, 40**).

The Pedra Azul State Park, located in the State of Espírito Santo, Brazil, has one of the main Brazilian geological heritages, a granite rock with 1,822 meters of altitude, known as Pedra Azul (literally Blue Stone). It has this name because depending on the incidence of sunlight, the rock can change color, sometimes turning blue or green, and even yellow [40-42] (**Photo 41**). The Cheile Bicazului Hășmaș National Park is of great scientific interest in geology, geomorphology, paleontology, landscape, and biology due to its variety of geoclimatic conditions. The park is located in the Hășmaș mountains, Romania, in the central group of the Eastern Carpathians, a mountain range also known as Moldo-Transylvanian Carpathians. The park is in the central-northeastern part of Romania, in the Neamț, and Harghita counties (**Photo 42**).

Yellowstone National Park, located in the western United States, is known for its wildlife, and its many geothermal features, especially the geysers. It spans an area of about 9,000 km², comprising lakes, canyons, rivers, and mountain ranges. Hundreds of species of mammals, birds, fish, reptiles, and amphibians have been documented, including several that are either endangered or threatened. The vast forests and grasslands also include unique species of plants. Yellowstone Park is the largest, and most famous megafauna location in the contiguous United States. Grizzly bears, cougars, wolves, and free-ranging herds of bison, and elk live in this park. The Yellowstone Park bison herd is the oldest, and largest public bison herd in the United States. Yellowstone is an incredibly complex place and a geologist's dream! The landscape of the Greater Yellowstone Ecosystem is the result of various geological processes over the last 150 million years. Here, Earth's crust has been compressed, pulled apart, glaciated, eroded, and subjected to volcanism. All this geologic activity formed the mountains, canyons, and plateaus that define the natural wonder that is Yellowstone National Park [43-45] (**Photos 43-46**).

Cappadocia Geopark covers the administrative borders of Nevşehir province, which forms the central part of the Cappadocia Volcanic Area in the Central Anatolian Region of Turkey. It is a geological, and cultural marvel, known for its unique rock formations, fairy chimneys, and underground cities, as well as its rich history dating back thousands of years. The geologic formations found in Cappadocia are the result of millions of years of volcanic activity, tectonic movements, and erosion. The landscape is characterized by soft, easily erodible volcanic tuff, which has been sculpted into a variety of shapes by the forces of wind, and water. One of the most notable features of Cappadocia is its rock-cut architecture. The soft

tuff, and volcanic ash that make up the region's geological formations are easy to carve, making it possible for people to create homes, churches, and other structures directly into the rock. The earliest examples of rock-cut architecture in Cappadocia date back to the Hittite period (18th to 12th centuries BC), and the tradition continued throughout the Byzantine era (4th to 15th centuries AD), resulting in an extensive network of underground cities, cave dwellings, and churches [46-49] (**Photos 47-50**).

Hydrodiversity

Hydrological diversity, or hydrodiversity, is the diversity of the surface water resources of the Earth and is included in the prevailing geodiversity concepts [50, 51]. It contains the spatial extents of permanent water, such as rivers, streams, lakes, seas, marshes, and snow cover [18]. Freshwater habitats account for some of the richest biodiversity in the world, and rivers are a vital, vibrant ecosystem for many species. Stream and river organisms reflect their localized niche, and surrounding landscape both upstream, and downstream. River organisms have evolved in diverse, and fascinating ways in the varied environments between river source, and mouth [52].

River sources are usually small, and in the case of mountain streams, steep, and erosional [53]. In temperate environments, small streams tend to be shaded by an interlocking, overhead tree canopy. Such conditions result in cool, well-oxygenated streams that are abundantly supplied with a food base of leaves. Fine particles of organic matter are released as the leaves are broken down by biological communities in the streams [52, 54]. Changes in physical habitat and food base from river source to mouth profoundly influence biological communities. Very large rivers are usually low gradient, and very wide, resulting in negligible influence of riparian canopy in terms of shading, and leaf-litter input. Water currents keep fine solids in suspension, reducing light penetration to the benthos. Organic matter in suspension is by far the largest food base in these very large rivers [52].

The Amazon basin is the part of South America drained by the Amazon River and its tributaries. The Amazon drainage basin covers an area of about 6,300,000 km², the equivalent of 60% of the European territory. Most of the basin is covered by the Amazon rainforest. There are more than 1,000 tributaries of the Amazon that flow into it from the Guiana Highlands, the Brazilian Highlands, and the Andes. Six of these tributaries: the Japurá, Juruá, Madeira, Negro, Purus, Tapajós, and Xingu rivers are each more than 1,600 km long. The Xingu River (**Photo 51**) is a southeast tributary of the Amazon River, and one of the largest clearwater rivers in the Amazon basin, accounting for about 5% of its water [55]. Formed by several rivers, and streams, the Xingu meanders generally northward for approximately 2,100 km, emptying into the Amazon River.

The Teles Pires River (**Photo 52**) rises in central Mato Grosso State and flows north-northwestward, where it joins the Juruena River to form the Tapajós River (**Photo 53**), an important tributary of the Amazon River. For 320 km the Teles Pires marks part of the state boundary between Pará, and Mato Grosso states. Its 1,400 km course is frequently interrupted by waterfalls and rapids. The Madeira River (**Photos 54, 55**) exceeds 3,200 km from source to mouth. It is the Amazon's largest, and most important tributary. Spanning about a quarter of the Brazilian Amazon, the Madeira Basin is a treasure trove of biodiversity, providing home to the spotted jaguar, giant otter, pink dolphin, and countless other endangered mammal species. The

river teems with life, an estimated 750 fish species migrate some 4,500 km each year to spawn and feed in the nutrient-rich, muddy waters of the upper Madeira [56-59].

The Negro River accounts for about one-fifth of the total discharge of the Amazon, and 40 percent of its aggregate volume is measured just below the confluence at Manaus. Near Manaus, the Rio Negro meets the Solimões River, forming the Meeting of the Waters (**Photo 56**), where the muddy waters of the Solimões do not mix with the waters of the Rio Negro. After the union of the two rivers, they started to receive the name “Rio Amazonas”, in Brazilian territory. The dark color of the waters of the Rio Negro, which contrasts with the muddy Solimões, is mainly due to its transparency, and the small amount of clay in suspension. For 6 km the waters of the two rivers run side by side without mixing [60, 61].

The Amazon River (**Photos 57, 58**) begins in the Andes Mountains. With a length of about 6,400 km before it drains into the Atlantic Ocean. It is the second longest river in the world, after the Nile River. The extensive lowland areas bordering the Amazon River, and its tributaries, called várzeas (“floodplains”), are subject to annual flooding, with consequent soil enrichment; however, most of the vast basin consists of upland, well above the inundations, and known as terra firme. More than two-thirds of the basin is covered by an immense rainforest, which grades into dry forest, and savanna on the higher northern, and southern margins, and into montane forest in the Andes to the west. The Amazon Rainforest, which represents about half of the Earth’s remaining rainforest, also constitutes its single largest reserve of biological resources. The Amazon rainforest and its rivers host an extraordinary variety of species, some endemic, others endangered, and many of which are still unknown. It is considered to be one of the areas on the planet with the greatest number of animal species. This biodiversity is very important globally, because as the largest biodiversity reserve in the world [62-67].

The Plitviče Lakes National Park, in Croatia (**Photos 59-62**), is world-famous for its sixteen lakes arranged in cascades. These lakes are a result of the junction of several small rivers and subterranean karst rivers. In the Plitviče Lakes, the tufa-formation process in which tufa barriers form, and grow is a highly complex process that has created the cascade lake system that includes several physiochemical, and biological factors. More than 1,400 plant taxa (species, and subspecies) have been recorded for the Plitviče Lakes National Park, which amounts to 30% of the entire Croatian flora. The fauna, which represents the wildlife of the Plitviče Lakes, is extremely rich, and diverse due to the conservation, and sustainability of the habitat. There are many species of insects, like 321 species of butterflies [68-72].

Triglav National Park (Triglavski Narodni Park in Slovene) is a wonderful national park in Slovenia (**Photo 63**) [73]. The main river in this park is the Soča, with 138 km that flows through western Slovenia, and northeastern Italy. The Soča river (**Photo 64**) is a true pearl of the Julian Alps and one of the most beautiful rivers in Europe. Lake Bohinj which lies in the heart of the Triglav National Park is the largest Slovenian natural lake, nested at the foot of unspoiled mountains, and mountain tops (**Photo 65**). It is the habitat of 53 species of planktonic algae, around 60 species of invertebrate fauna, and at least 16 species of fish [74]. Zelenci Springs is a nature reserve near the town of Kranjska Gora. It is the source of the Sava Dolinka River. At Zelenci Springs, water from underground Nadiža Creek (originating in the Planica Valley) re-emerges through the porous bottom of a 2 m deep lake, whose waters are noted for their deep, brilliant green [75] (**Photo 66**). The spring and its surrounding area are named after this color (Zelenci is a deadjectival plural noun from Slovene zelen 'green'). The area of the nature reserve is 47 hectares and is home to numerous endangered animal, and plant species. Near Kobarid, above the emerald green Soča River, there is a gorge of the Kozjak stream, where

the 15-meter-high Kozjak Waterfall particularly stands out. This natural sight creates the image of a heavenly corner hidden from the everyday world by tall, dark walls, covered in limestone sediments, just like in the karstic caves. An arranged footpath will lead you to the waterfall (**Photos 67-69**).

Mammoth Lakes is a great base camp for exploring all the things that make the mountains of California extraordinary. Yosemite National Park is a short drive away. Mammoth Lakes is a great base camp for exploring all the things that make the mountains of California extraordinary. There is no official Mammoth Lake, but there are several wonderful lakes in the Mammoth Lakes Basin, such as Twin Lakes (**Photos 70-82**). Old Faithful may be more famous, but the Grand Prismatic Hot Spring is the most photographed thermal feature in Yellowstone National Park. That's because of its crazy-bright colors, and enormous size. The hot spring has bright bands of orange, yellow, and green that ring the deep blue waters in the spring. The multicolored layers get their hues from different species of thermophile (heat-loving) bacteria living in the progressively cooler water around the spring., and the deep blue center? That's because water scatters the blue wavelengths of light more than others, reflecting blues to our eyes (**Photos 83-76**).

Biodiversity

The term biological diversity was used first in "The Variable Desert" [76]: "The bare statement that the region contains a flora rich in genera, and species, and of diverse geographic origin or affinity is entirely inadequate as a description of its real biological diversity." Biodiversity is most used to replace the more clearly defined, and long-established terms, species diversity, and species richness. Biodiversity is taken to be the integration of biological variability across all scales, from the genetic, through species, and ecosystems, to landscapes [77]. Biologists most often define biodiversity as the "totality of genes, species, and ecosystems of a region. An advantage of this definition is that it presents a unified view of the traditional types of biological variety previously identified: taxonomic diversity, usually measured at the species diversity level [78]; ecological diversity, often viewed from the perspective of ecosystem diversity [78]; morphological diversity, which stems from genetic diversity, and molecular diversity [79];, and functional diversity, which is a measure of the number of functionally disparate species within a population, e.g. different feeding mechanism [80]. Biodiversity refers to every living thing, including plants, bacteria, animals, and humans. Scientists have estimated that there are around 8.7 million species of plants and animals in existence. However, only around 1.2 million species have been identified, and described so far, most of which are insects.

The diversity of fauna is more directly correlated with the structure of the forest than the quantity of plant species in the natural environment [81]. Tropical forests possess a large variation of internal microclimates, taking advantage of both its horizontal, and vertical structure. The increase in structural complexity of the vegetation on various vertical levels makes new forms of occupancy of the environment possible. The increase in the number of animal species is principally due to the increase of both the new food guilds, and the number of species in the existing guilds [82].

The composition of the fauna is the product of an evolutionary process. Each animal species is dependent on certain characteristics of the vegetation, and the biological interactions that determine where it will be able to exist [83]. The structure of the forest, the distance

between trees, the different types of vegetation, as well as the special arrangement of the forest elements that constitute the landscape determine the patterns of movement of these animals and explain a large part of the spatial variation in the number, and categories of tree visits.

Among the many factors thought to contribute to the high bird species richness in the Neotropics is the high diversity of habitat, and microhabitat types, some of which are unique to tropical regions [84, 85]. The increase in structural complexity of the vegetation on various vertical levels makes new forms of occupancy of the environment possible [86]. The increase in the number of bird species is principally due to the increase of both the new food guilds, and the number of species in the existing guilds [82].

The integrity, and complexity of a forest are the factors that influence the composition, abundance, and probably the functions of the assembly of different bird species. In that way, in forest environments where a vertical stratification of resources occurs, these species are distributed occupying a high diversity of trophic niches. They occupy different heights of the forest, and a great diversity of bird species distributed among different trophic guilds, which means ecosystems are relatively balanced, and of great biological value. The diversity, and density of the frugivorous, and omnivorous birds in medium, and advanced stages of ecological succession in the forest fragments could be directly correlated not only with the structure of the forest but also to the fact that these birds feed almost exclusively on abundant, and easy to find food source: shrub, and tree fruit of certain vegetable species abundant in rainforest understory layer [64, 87-89].

Much interaction exists between vegetation, and fauna since most tropical tree species are pollinated by animals [90]. In the same way, the dispersion of tropical tree species' seeds, in many cases, can be associated with the interaction with animals. Various research projects done in the riparian forests have shown a high predominance of zoochory among species. Trees attract different species of seed-dispersing frugivorous animals according to the number of resources that they offer or because these animals use them as rest areas, nesting grounds, or shelter.

Plants used as a food source possess adaptations to attract and repel their consumers [91]. Many of them possess fruits, and seeds with certain characteristics aimed at attracting, and stimulating the appetite of fauna. Among these attractive characteristics of fruit are color, size, form, chemical components, type of inflorescence, abundance, accessibility, type of habitat, and distance between fruit-bearing plants [92]. In this context the fruit would have evolved to facilitate their use, favoring dispersion, and germination of their seeds far from the mother plant, thus minimizing competition for space, and protecting them from destructive consumption [93].

Some areas in the world have more biodiversity than others. Areas with extremely high levels of biodiversity are called hotspots. Endemic species, that are only found in one particular location, are also found in hotspots. The Amazon Rainforest is one of the principal Brazilian biomes, and is formed by dense tropical forests, and associated ecosystems, and represents over half of the planet's remaining rainforests, and comprises the largest, and most biodiverse tract of tropical rainforest in the world. An immense number of bird species live in the Amazon rainforest, with over 1,300 species, which accounts for one-third of all bird species in the world. Much scientific research carried out in the Amazon demonstrates its richness in avifauna [94-107]. Caatinga is a type of subtropical vegetation and an ecoregion characterized by this vegetation in interior northeastern Brazil. Caatinga harbors a unique biota, with thousands of endemic species. It contains over 1,000 vascular plant species in addition to 221 bee species,

241 fish species, 177 reptile species, 79 amphibian species, 591 bird species, and 178 mammal species [108-120].

The Brazilian Savanna (Cerrado biome) presents a great diversity of several different groups of organisms, and, for this reason, is considered one of the most important endemism areas of South America [121]. This fact, together with the high level of disturbance in this biome, resulted in the inclusion of the Cerrado among the 25 hotspots of world biodiversity. The number of vascular plants is greater than that found in most regions of the world: herbaceous, shrubs, and arboreal plants, and vines represent more than 7,000 species [122]. The Atlantic Forest is one of the most important biodiversity hotspots; originally covering over 1.3 million km², distributed along the Brazilian coast, and is the most threatened Brazilian biome. This important biome harbors a high diversity of bird species, with several endemic, and threatened species [123] (**Photos 77-130**).

The photos presented in this report were realized by Fabio Rossano Dario, and Cristina De Vincenzo, using a digital photo camera Canon PowerShot.

CONCLUSIONS

In a society that prioritizes intellectual, and creative work, it is necessary to awaken the intellect, through spiritual stimuli, and the contemplation of natural resources, in carrying out activities that provide moments of peace, and enjoyment of the environment, and the senses.

Understanding the landscape with the appreciation of the elements that constitute it, through knowledge of the main plant, and animal species, interspecific interactions, water, and geological resources, history, and culture of traditional peoples of the places we visited will contribute to a better contemplation of these environments, and consequently the valorization, and dissemination of natural, and cultural heritage.

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Photo 1. Located in Arizona, U.S., the Grand Canyon National Park receives around 5.5 million people each year. It is a natural formation made up of layers of red rock, which reveal millions of years of geological history in cross section.

Photo 2. Nearly 40 identified rock layers form the Grand Canyon's walls. They have attracted students of earth history since 1858.

Photo 3. Layered bands of colorful rock reveal millions of years of geologic history with unmatched vistas from the rim in Grand Canyon National Park.

Photo 4. Resting with an amazing panoramic view in Grand Canyon National Park.

Photo 5. Grand Canyon is one of the most studied geologic landscapes in the world. It offers an excellent record of three of the four eras of geological time.

Photo 6. Red-brown, and gray conglomerate of well-rounded to subangular pebbles, and boulders of granite, gneiss, and schist derived from underlying Early Proterozoic igneous, and metamorphic rocks.

Photo 7. The red rocks of Sedona, Arizona, U.S., are formed by a unique layer of rock known as the Schnebly Hill formation.

Photo 8. Before the red-colored rocks turned into stone, the Sedona landscape was all mushy mud, and sand. Over a 320-million-year period, changes in the environment helped transform the sand, and mud into something more impressive than you could have envisioned.

Photo 9. The Courthouse Butte in Sedona is one of the many breathtaking red rock formations that can be found throughout this area.

Photo 10. The famous red rocks in, and around Sedona are, for the most part, the same layers that make up the upper walls of the Grand Canyon.

Photo 11. Mount Triglav (2,864 m) is the highest summit of the Julian Alps, and Slovenia. To Slovenes, it represents a prime national symbol.

Photo 12. Planica Valley is a beautiful glacial valley in the Triglav National Park, in the northern part of the Slovenian Julian Alps.

Photo 13. The Planica Valley is located between 2,500-meter-high mountains in the northern part of the Triglav National Park, next to the alpine village of Kranjska Gora, Slovenia

Photo 14. The Planica Valley, in Slovenia, is a real tourist magnet, not only for mountaineering, and climbing but also for family-friendly cycling, and hiking.

Photo 15. In the state of Utah, as in Arizona, U.S., beautiful geological formations dominate the landscape.

Photo 16. In the mountains of Zion National Park, in Utah, U.S., the tourist can contemplate at massive sandstone cliffs of cream, ...

Photo 17. ... pink, and red that soar into a brilliant blue sky.

Photo 18. The Zion National Park, Utah, U.S., is a great example of a geological park. Most of the rocks in this park are sedimentary rocks, made from pieces of older rocks that have been weathered, eroded, and deposited in layers.

Photo 19. Zabriskie Point is a part of the Amargosa Range located east of Death Valley in Death Valley National Park in California, United States.

Photo 20. View of Zabriskie Point, California, U.S., showing convolutions, texture, and color contrasts in the eroded rock.

Photo 21. Death Valley is a desert valley in Eastern California, U.S.. It is thought to be the hottest place on Earth during summer.

Photo 22. Panoramic view from Death Valley, in California, U.S.

Photo 23. Death Valley is a down dropped block of land between two mountain ranges. It lies at the southern end of a geological trough called Walker Lane, which runs north to Oregon.

Photo 24. In this below-sea-level basin, steady drought, and record summer heat make Death Valley, in California, a land of extremes, reaching 54 °C, considered the highest temperature on Earth.

Photo 25. The landscape of Yosemite National Park, in California, U.S., is a product of its unique geology, resulting from glacial erosion of the underlying granite.

Photo 26. Yosemite National Park is the natural home to many lakes.

Photo 27. El Capitan's iconic granite walls dominate the west end of Yosemite Valley. At more than 900 m above the valley floor, it is more than 3 times as high as the top of the Eiffel Tower.

Photo 28. Yosemite National Park is located within the heart of the Sierra Nevada, the largest fault-block mountain range in the United States.

Photo 29. Sierra Nevada, in California, U.S., is an asymmetric mountain range with gradual western slopes, and steep eastern crags.

Photo 30. Examples of glacial formations in the Sierra Nevada abound for those willing to learn how to recognize them and seek them out.

Photo 31. Steamboat Rock State Park, Washington State, U.S. Carved by Ice Age floods into a dramatic, lake-dotted canyon, Steamboat Rock State Park's landscape dates back at least 13,000 years.

Photo 32. Detail of the Steamboat Rock, a basalt butte that rises 240 m. Basalt is an aphanitic extrusive igneous rock formed from the rapid cooling of low-viscosity lava rich in magnesium, and iron exposed at surface.

Photo 33. Once the world's largest waterfall, Dry Falls, in Washington State, U.S., now an oasis in the desert. According to the current geological model, catastrophic flooding channeled water through the Upper Grand Coulee, and over this 120 m rock face at the end of the last glaciation.

Photo 34. Today, Dry Falls remains spectacular even without the water.

Photo 35. Serra da Capivara National Park, located in the State of Piauí, Brazil, is one of the main geoparks in Latin America.

Photo 36. The Serra da Capivara borders two major geological formations: the Maranhão-Piauí sediment basin, and the peripheral depression of the São Francisco River.

Photo 37. The Serra da Capivara is endowed with a diversity of relief vegetation, and landscapes of breathtaking beauty, and dotted with exceptional views of the surrounding valleys, and mountains.

Photo 38. Serra da Capivara National Park, in Brazil, has beautiful rock formations, where you can find archaeological, and paleontological sites.

Photo 39. Many of the numerous rock shelters in the Serra da Capivara National Park are decorated with cave paintings, some of which are over 25,000 years old.

Photo 40. These cave paintings in the Serra da Capivara, Brazil, are an excellent testimony of one of the oldest human communities in South America.

Photo 41. The Pedra Azul State Park has one of the main Brazilian geological heritages, a granite rock with 1,822 meters of altitude, known as Pedra Azul. Granite is a coarse-grained intrusive igneous rock composed mostly of quartz, alkali feldspar, and plagioclase. It forms from magma with a high content of silica, and alkali metal oxides that slowly cools, and solidifies.

Photo 42. Cheile Bicazului Hășmaș National Park, in Romania, is of great scientific interest in geology, geomorphology, paleontology, landscape, and biology.

Photo 43. Yellowstone National Park, located in the western United States, is known for its wildlife, and its many geothermal features, especially the geysers. Geyser is a thermal spring that erupts periodically, releasing a column of hot water, and steam.

Photo 44. The landscape of the greater Yellowstone ecosystem is the result of various geological processes over the last 150 million years.

Photo 45. Detail of the yellow rocks seen in the Grand Canyon of the Yellowstone National Park.

Photo 46. Great Falls of the Yellowstone National Park.

Photo 47. Cappadocia is a region located in central Turkey that is famous for its unique geological formations.

Photo 48. As the landscape continued to evolve, the erosion of the tuff created a network of valleys, canyons, and distinctive rock formations, including “fairy chimneys”: tall, cone-shaped rock spires with a capstone on top.

Photo 49. In addition to the fairy chimneys, Cappadocia is also home to many other interesting geological features, including rock cones, valleys, canyons, and underground cities.

Photo 50. One of the most notable features of Cappadocia, Turkey, is its rock-cut architecture.

Photo 51. The Xingu River is one of the largest clearwater rivers in the Amazon basin, located in the Brazilian Amazon rainforest. It is approximately 2,000 kilometers long.

Photo 52. The Teles Pires River rises in central Mato Grosso State, Brazil, and flows north-northwestward, where it joins the Juruena River to form the Tapajós River, an important tributary of the Amazon River.

Photo 53. Meeting of Waters: confluence between the dark (blackwater) Tapajós River, and the pale sandy-colored (whitewater) Amazon River, in the city of Santarém, Pará State, Brazil.

Photo 54. The Madeira River, in Brazilian Amazon rainforest, exceeds 3,200 kilometers from source to mouth. It is the Amazon's largest, and most important tributary.

Photo 55. Amazonas River, and the mouth of the Madeira River, Brazilian Amazon rainforest.

Photo 56. Meeting of Waters: confluence between the dark (blackwater) Negro River, and the pale sandy-colored (whitewater) Amazon River, in Manaus, Amazonas State, Brazil. For six kilometers the waters of the two rivers run side by side without mixing.

Photo 57. Sunset on the Amazon River, in Brazil, the second longest river in the world, with approximately 7,000 kilometers in length.

Photo 58. Detail of a boat on a small tributary of the Amazon River.

Photo 59. A barrier between the lakes Gavanovac, and Kaluđerovac, in the Plitviče Lakes National Park, Croatia.

Photo 60. Bog habitats, and their vegetation in Croatia, as well as in the Plitviče Lakes National Park, are relics of the glacial period.

Photo 61. Small waterfalls like these are located throughout the Plitviče Lakes National Park, Croatia.

Photo 62. The European chub (*Squalius cephalus*) is in clean water. Observe the lucidity, and clarity of the water in the Plitviče Lakes National Park, Croatia.

Photo 63. Triglav National Park (Triglavski Narodni Park in Slovene) is Slovenia's largest protected area.

Photo 64. The Soča river is the “emerald beauty” that inspired the poet Simon Gregorčič to write his best-known poem, considered one of the masterpieces of Slovene poetry.

Photo 65. Lake Bohinj which lies in the heart of the Triglav National Park is the largest Slovenian natural lake, nestled at the foot of unspoilt mountains, and mountain tops.

Photo 66. At Zelenci Springs, Slovenia, water from underground Nadiža Creek re-emerges through the porous bottom of a two meters deep lake, whose waters are noted for their deep, brilliant green.

Photo 67. Detail of the emerald green Kozjak stream, Slovenia.

Photo 68. The mystical view of the rocky amphitheater with the green pool, and the white beam of water of the Kozjak Waterfall, Slovenia.

Photo 69. Observing the natural beauties of the Triglav National Park, Slovenia.

Photo 70. Twin Lakes is nestled between Panorama Dome, and the steep southern flank of Mammoth Mountain, in Mammoth Lakes, California, U.S.

Photo 71. Mammoth Lakes, in California, is known for its beautiful alpine lakes that boast crystal blue water with stunning mountainscapes in the background.

Photo 72. Mammoth Lakes, California is one of those places you must see to still not totally believe.

Photo 73. The landscape of the Greater Yellowstone Ecosystem is the result of various geological processes over the last 150 million years.

Photo 74. Hot springs are the most common hydrothermal features in Yellowstone National Park.

Photo 75. Grand Prismatic Hot Spring is the most photographed thermal feature in Yellowstone National Park, U.S.

Photo 76. Morning Glory Pool is a hot spring in the Yellowstone Upper Geyser Basin.

Photo 77. The Iguazu National Park in Brazil, in addition to the impressive waterfalls, is home to a rich biodiversity, with rare, and endangered species, and the largest population of jaguars in the Atlantic Forest.

Photo 78. Serra do Mar State Park represents the largest preserved continuous portion of the Atlantic Forest in Brazil.

Photo 79. *Galbula ruficauda*, ♂, Galbulidae (airamba; Rufous-tailed Jacamar). It is a species of wide distribution in Brazil.

Photo 80. *Ramphastos toco*, Ramphastidae (tucanucu; Toco Toucan). It is a species of wide distribution in Brazil. It is resting on a cedro branch (*Cedrela fissilis*) in full fruition.

Photo 81. *Callithrix geoffroyi* is a species of tamarin endemic to the Atlantic forest of southeastern Brazil.

Photo 82. *Callithrix jacchus* is a species of tamarin native to the shrubby forests of the Caatinga, and the Atlantic forest of northeastern Brazil.

Photo 83. *Cupania vernalis* is a tree native to Brazil, from the Sapindaceae family. Its seeds are covered by an edible orange aril that promotes its dispersion by several species of animals.

Photo 84. The lizard *Salvator merianae*, known as “teiú” is the largest lizard found in Brazil, and can reach 1.4 meters in total length.

Photo 85. The caxinguelê (*Sciurus aestuans*), also called serelepe or quatipuru is known in English as "Brazilian squirrel".

Photo 86. The Amazon rainforest, which covers much of northwest Brazil, and extends to Colombia, Peru, and other countries in South America, is the largest rainforest in the world, famous for its biodiversity.

Photo 87. Aerial view of the Amazon Rainforest in the state of Mato Grosso.

Photo 88. The Amazon Rainforest has “várzeas” (seasonally flooded lands) along the margins of the of major rivers, its tributaries, and igarapés (small creeks).

Photo 89. *Theobroma speciosum*, known as “cacaú” is one of the cocoa species of the Amazon Rainforest.

Photo 90. *Pteroglossus aracari*, Ramphastidae (aracari-de-bico-branco; Black-necked Aracari). This species is present in the Amazon, and Atlantic Forests.

Photo 91. The collared peccary (*Pecari tajacu*) is a pig native to the Americas, which occurs throughout Brazil.

Photo 92. Chapada dos Guimarães National Park is located in Mato Grosso, Brazil. The steep edge prominent relief of the Chapada dos Guimarães was developed in Devonian, and Juro-Cretaceous.

Photo 93. The Myrtaceae is one of the main families of the Brazilian Savanna, both in several species, and density of trees, and shrubs.

Photo 94. *Triplaris americana* is a tree in the botanical family Polygonaceae known by many common names, including pau-formiga ("ant tree").

Photo 95. Fruit of *Sterculia apetala*, commonly known as manduvi, is a tree species in the family Malvaceae.

Photo 96. *Crotalus durissus*, known as "cascavel" or South American rattlesnake, is a highly venomous pit viper species found in South America. It is the most widely distributed member of its genus.

Photo 97. Detail of the lizard *Tapinurus helenae*, recorded in the Serra da Capivara National Park, State of Piauí, Brazil...

Photo 98. ..., and its representation in cave painting more than 10,000 years ago.

Photo 99. Detail of vegetation from the Caatinga biome, in Brazil. The caatinga vegetation is formed by xerophytic plants, such as cacti, adapted to desert, and semi-arid climates.

Photo 100. *Melocactus* (melon cactus) is a genus of cactus with about 30-40 species, with a concentration of species in northeastern Brazil, in the Caatinga biome.

Photo 101. The lichens are an important element of the biodiversity of the Caatinga, Brazil. Detail of species from the Parmeliaceae family.

Photo 102. *Tropidurus hispidus* is a lizard species that are widely distributed in Brazil. It is commonly known in Northeast Brazil as “catende”.

Photo 103. The Mono Basin, in Mono Basin National Forest is an endorheic drainage basin located east of Yosemite National Park in California, and Nevada, U.S.

Photo 104. The House Wren (*Troglodytes aedon*) is a very small songbird of the wren family. It occurs from Canada to southernmost South America and is thus the most widely distributed native bird in the Americas.

Photo 105. The White-crowned Sparrow (*Zonotrichia leucophrys*) is a species of passerine bird native to North America. These birds forage on the ground or in low vegetation, but sometimes make short flights to catch flying insects. They mainly eat seeds, other plant parts, and insects.

Photo 106. The biggest bird in Arizona is the California Condor (*Gymnogyps californianus*), with a wingspan of up to 8 feet (3 meters). It has suffered at the hand of persecution, lead poisoning, and habitat destruction. It has held mythological and cultural significance to Native American tribes, and interestingly the perception of it differs from tribe to tribe. This condor was registered on the Navajo Bridge (36°49' N; 111°37' S) on 28th May, 2016.

Photo 107. Registering the natural beauties of the Grand Canyon National Park, U.S.

Photo 108. Detail of registered flower.

Photo 109. Like other jays, Steller's Jays (*Cyanocitta stelleri*) are bold, inquisitive, intelligent, and noisy. Steller's Jays spend much of their time exploring the forest canopy, flying with patient wingbeats. They come to the forest floor to investigate visitors, and look for food, moving with decisive hops of their long legs. It is a species of passerine bird native to North America.

Photo 110. The Western Scrub-jay (*Aphelocoma californica*) feed on small animals, such as frogs, and lizards, eggs, and young of other birds, insects, grains, nuts, and berries. Scrub jays are the only non-primate or non-dolphin shown to plan for the future, known as metacognition. It is a species of passerine bird native to North America.

Photo 111. Going on a hike is a wonderful way to experience some of the rich natural beauty present in national parks, and protected reserves, such as the Grand Canyon National Park.

Photo 112. Elk (*Cervus elaphus*) is the largest member of the deer family (Cervidae) in Grand Canyon National Park.

Photo 113. Because most layers are exposed through the Canyon's thereabout 450 km, they allow detailed studies of environmental changes from place to place (within a layer) in the geologic past.

Photo 114. Virtually every square foot of the Grand Canyon National Park would fall into these three categories: plants, scenery, and wildlife.

Photo 115. Grand Canyon cacti most commonly have flowers of red, purple or yellow. The majority grow in the inner canyon, although several species are found on the rim.

Photo 116. Viñales National Park, in Cuba, is formed by mogotes. The mogotes are generally-isolated steep-sided residual hills, surrounded by nearly flat alluvial plains. These hills typically have a rounded, tower-like form.

Photo 117. The Redwood National Park, located in California's North Coast is the home to the tallest trees on Earth. The redwood forest has trees (*Sequoia sempervirens*) up to 84 meters high.

Photo 118. Yellowstone National Park, in Wyoming, U.S. is the only place continuously inhabited by bison since prehistoric times, and the species numbers nearly 5,000.

Photo 119. Yellowstone National Park may be the only location in the United States where free-ranging bison were never extirpated, since they continued to exist in the wild, and were not reintroduced.

Photo 120. The pronghorn (*Antilocapra americana*) is a species of artiodactyl mammal to interior western, and central North America. It is the only surviving member of the family Antilocapridae.

Photo 121. African baobab trees, scientifically known as *Adansonia digitata*, are some of the oldest living organisms in the world. This tree was photographed in the interior of Angola.

Photo 122. The baobab flowers are large, pendulous, white in color, with curved petals, and numerous stamens. It has a sweet scent, but as time goes by, they acquire a peculiar bad smell, reminiscent of carrion. They last from one to two days and are pollinated by bats.

Photo 123. In the Plitviče Lakes National Park, in Croatia, the tufa-formation process in which tufa barriers form, and grow is highly complex.

Photo 124. The white butterbur (*Petasites albus*) is a plant species in the family Asteraceae. It is native to central Europe, and the Caucasus. It prefers damp soils in deciduous forests, mountain pastures, and streamsides.

Photo 125. The beech (*Fagus sylvatica*) is one of the predominant tree species in the Triglav National Park, in Slovenia.

Photo 126. Detail of a branch of beech (*Fagus sylvatica*).

Photo 127. Small-leaved lime (*Tilia cordata*), tree species registered in the Triglav National Park, in Slovenia.

Photo 128. Detail of a branch with flowers of small-leaved lime (*Tilia cordata*).

Photo 129. *Podarcis muralis*, species of lizard registered in the Triglav National Park, Slovenia, has scales highly variable in color, and pattern. Its coloration is brownish or greyish and may occasionally be tinged with green.

Photo 130. In addition to species from the plant, and animal world, the Triglav National Park is also abundant in fungi species. Fungi are a large, and very significant group of organisms.